

Do Core Self - Evaluation Impact Every Job - Outcomes? Test the Moderating Role of Organizational Socialization: Empirical Studies in the Newcomer's Context at a Government Organization

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ABSTRACT

Is there organization socialization as a moderating relationship? The study involved 159 newcomers to the Aceh Besar District Government organization. Primary data was obtained by distributing questionnaires online to respondents through Google forms. Moderation Regression Analysis (MRA) and Multiple Regression were used in this research analysis method. The results show that Core Self-Evaluation from new entrants has a positive impact on each work outcome. Furthermore, organizational socialization supports the relationship, but the role of organizational socialization is not proven to achieve better job satisfaction.

Keywords: Business environment, Construction services, External and internal factors.

INTRODUCTION

Public administration is closely related to public services. The role of public administration is very important to support human resource competencies to be more effective, especially newcomers. The quality of life of government organizations depends not only on public administration but also on the will of the individual [1]. Research on core self-evaluation is an idea offered to strengthen public administration, especially in government organizations, because we believe it can have an impact on outcomes.

Studies on core self-evaluation which are considered to have an impact on job-outcomes have been widely carried out, but research in the context of newcomers in an organization has not been given attention by them.

Therefore, Narayan and Johnson suggestion to researchers was to take the focus of further research on the socialization process in the context of a newcomer or to a new team [2]. This is because the understanding of most organizations about the importance of socialization is still very limited Organizational socialization (OS) is one process through which employees learn the information needed to make a successful transition into an integrated member of the organization. Several studies have examined (OS) which has a direct impact on job outcomes, but the role (OS) as a moderating relationship has not been given attention by them.

The present study wants to examine more deeply about OS, which examines as moderating the relationship between core self-evaluation and job-outcomes in the context of new workers

(newcomers) [3]. Although this study considers core self-evaluation not necessarily increasing job-outcomes for newcomers, there is however other variables that are considered potentially more powerful in encouraging core self-evaluation behavior which in turn increases job-outcomes for newcomers in an organization.

REVIEW OF PREVIOUS STUDIES

Core self-evaluations (CSEs) and job-outcomes

According to the Core self-evaluations (CSEs) are a broad personality trait. The concept of CSEs is a high-level nature that represents the primary evaluations and assumptions such as their worthiness, competence, and abilities people make about themselves. The concept of CSEs is in the development of the concepts of "Self-Esteem" and "Self-Efficacy". Some researchers use this concept to explore the constructs of CSEs.

Job outcomes can be investigated from several perspectives [4]. Many authors use the terms job outcomes or work outcomes that indicate the characteristics of a job.

According to Oldham and Fried, the job characteristic theory (JCT) provides a theoretical framework that can be tested and explains the effects of job characteristics on employee job outcomes (eg, internal motivation, job satisfaction, and performance). These characteristics are key to human resource management because most of the main dependent variables in the fields of psychology and management include job satisfaction, organizational commitment,

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performance, creativity, and more. Taylor analyzes job outcomes from aspects of job satisfaction and organizational commitment in a survey of social attitudes in Australia.

This study investigates the role of OS on the relationship of CSEs and job-outcomes [Job satisfaction (JSAT), organizational commitment (OC), and job performance (JP)] in the newcomer context. Several studies have been conducted which highlight broad personality traits called "Core self-evaluation [5]. The impact of CSEs on academic performance. Zhao et al., highlighted the effect of social support on CSEs. Dai et al., also highlighted the stronger the CSEs of employees, the greater their business behavior.

The moderating effect of CSE studies was conducted in China, Denmark, and the US. Jiang et al., found CSEs to positively influence life satisfaction and bring important theoretical and practical implications. Also, CSEs are predictors of lower psychological pressure and higher welfare outcomes. Nguyen and Borteyrou found CSEs to be strongly associated with job satisfaction.

Organizational Socialization as a Moderator

Moderator variables are variables that are considered to be able to reduce or modulate the magnitude of the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable, functioning as a neutralizing or balancing force for (something). Based on this view, this study wants to examine how OS plays its role in the behavior of newcomer CSEs in achieving its job-outcomes. Therefore this study places the OS as a moderator variable.

New or old employees in achieving certain outcomes are influenced by CSEs. CSEs are characteristic of attitudes possessed by workers which are displayed differently in their work environment. Based on their study CSEs do not show an impact on performance [6]. From these findings, it can be understood that CSEs need some kind of OS support in achieving better job-outcomes. Some researchers consider that employees who have CSEs are important. CSEs will function properly if human resource managers organize it. This study wants to investigate the seriousness of the application of OS by those who have authority in the organization where the unit of analysis of this study is studied, and OS is placed as a moderator variable.

Newcomer Context

Organizational socialization of newcomers is the topic of this research. Socialization is important both from individual employees and from an organizational perspective.

Adjusting new employees into an organization, the organization must pay special attention and time to facilitate them, whether new employees are organized as a whole or employees who are transferred, or promoted who take on an entirely new role within the organization. In handling a job there is a transition that is felt by new employees, this is caused by environmental situations that are not yet well recognized by them and the ability and experience factors are often challenges that are not expected by them.

Something strange and astonished is often experienced by those who have just entered into the organization or new team they know. We can surmise that they are experiencing an uncomfortable mood this will affect psychological and physiological effects which ultimately impact the achievement of outcomes that are not optimal, which were initially expected.

Therefore this study investigates CSE, Job-outcomes, and OS in the context of newcomers because we are very confident in getting a good reception from those interested in knowledge of human resources and organizational behavior [7]. Organizational socialization is an aspect highlighted in this research because this aspect can become a more advanced organization. Besides being able to help improve skills in line with what is needed and integrated into the organization, organizational socialization carried out seriously by organizations can have a positive impact on their performance.

METHOD

A total of 159 new employees from the results of recruitment in 2018 and 2019 at non-profit organizations under the authority of the Aceh Besar District government, were selected as participants [8]. Based on the small number of units analyzed, all populations were analyzed using the census sampling method. All participants were identified as new employees through the database of human resources at the institution. The questionnaire was sent via Whatsapp using Googleform and all data showed relevant for analysis purposes. Of 159 respondents, 60 (37.7%) were male, 99 (62.3%) female. 80 respondents (50.3%) were aged 20-30, 79 (49.7 %) were aged 31-35. 32 (20.1%) had Associate's Degree, 125 (78.6%) were undergraduate, only 2 (1.3%) were postgraduate. All of them have been working for < 2 years.

Obtaining primary and secondary data began with a letter of request from our research institute to the Aceh Besar District Government Authority. The data was formatted using the googleform application and then submitted to respondents via Whatsapp which is known from the employee database. Respondents are notified of the intent and purpose of the investigation and explain the term variable in question. All primary data were completely collected in one month (25 working days), including re-contacting to ensure the accuracy of the data provided [9].

Measurement

Core self-evaluation (CSE)

CSE size is determined based on the explanation of Judge et al., four indicators were selected for this scale and the results of the reliability test using Cronbach's alpha formula obtained a value of 0.73 [10]. An example statement is "I believe I have the success that I deserve in life".

Job satisfaction (JSAT)

Establishing five indicators to measure JSAT. Using Cronbach's alpha formula, the results of the reliability test obtained had a value of 0.76. Examples of statements are: "I feel satisfied doing work according to my ability".

Organizational commitment (OC)

The variable, organizational commitment in this investigation focuses on the dimensions of an effective organizational commitment. This dimension is considered relatively relevant to the research analysis unit. For the OC scale, five indicators were selected from the 12 scale indicators from the opinion of Meyer et al. An example statement is: "I would love to develop my career with this organization". The reliability test results of this indicator Obtained Cronbach's alpha value of 0.83.

Job performance (JP)

JP is measured by five scale indicators adopted from two previous researchers and then developed according to the unit of analysis of this study. Examples of statements are: "I feel able to complete the work according to the standards required by this organization". Cronbach's alpha value for this scale is 0.86.

Organizational Socialization (OS)

The measurement of organizational socialization was based on previous research and adopted from Chao et al., From the 3 indicators measured by them; we developed them into 5 question indicators that were adjusted to the analysis unit of this study. Examples of questions are: "Socialization of work by organizations is beneficial to me [11]. Cronbach's alpha reliability test results for this indicator were obtained 0.86.

Analysis

Using SPSS, analyzes of primary data were carried out. First, to find out the reliability of the research questionnaire carried out through the index formula (Cronbach's alpha). Second, to find out the validity of a research construct, validity testing was carried out. Third, to find out whether there is a direct influence of independent and dependent variables, and the influence of the moderating variables on the relationship, multiple regression analysis and moderated regression analysis (MRA) was used. In the end, the proof of the research hypothesis was interpreted from the results of this analysis.

Preliminary analysis

A validity test is a test of the accuracy or accuracy of a measuring instrument in measuring what you want to be measured. The validity test in this study used the product-moment correlation technique developed by Pearson [12]. If r arithmetic r table then the research construct is valid, or vice versa (Table 1).

Analysis descriptive and correlation

The descriptive statistical test results showed no extreme Value of the two measures - the mean and standard deviation of each of the variables analyzed [13]. As such, the conclusion reached is that the mean and standard deviation are relatively stable in the number of samples measured [14]. Furthermore, the results of correlation analysis between the variables showed each variable had a positive

correlation at the 0.01 significance level. From these results, all independent variables can be used to predict the dependent variable (Table 2).

Direct influence regression analysis

Explains the magnitude of the effect of the independent Variable (CSE) on three dependent variables (JSAT, OC, and JP), without moderation variables [15]. Based on the table, it can be seen that the value of 'adjusted R square', is, 0.237; 0.515; and 0.131 At the level of significance ($p < 0.01$). This means that CSE can influence the dependent variable, respectively (JSAT 23.7%; OC 51.5%; and JP 13.1%), while the rest (76.3%; 48.5%; and 86.9%) are influenced by other factors outside this model [16].

Larger OC variables can be predicted by CSE (more than 50%), it can be understood that the resource management system considers CSE more to achieve organizational goals, so organizational commitment for new employees is the main thing. Wulandari, found that organizational commitment contributes an important role in the organization.

Moderated regression analyses (MRA)

The results of the MRA analysis explain the extent to Which the variable (OS) plays a role as moderating the relationship between CSE and JSAT, OC, and JP. Here it can be explained that the value of the 'adjusted R square' direct effect between CSE on JSAT is 0.237 (23.7%) while the effect of CSE on JSAT after being interfered by OS (interaction) has decreased to 0.233 (23.3%). This means that the role of the OS weakens the relationship between CSE and JSAT and this role does not indicate significance.

The OS has the role of moderating the relationship between CSE and OC and JP. This can be seen in Table 4, where the value of 'adjusted R square' (models 1b and c) of 0.531 (53.1%) and 0.891 (89.1%) is an increase compared to the direct effect of 0.515 (51.5%) and 0.131 (13.1%) [17]. the role of OS based on models 1b and c in is significant at levels $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$.

The OS contribution to CSE and JP relations is very high, almost reaching 100%, it can be understood that, in general, performance improvement is the main objective of the organization.

Display summary of the results of the analysis in which explain the role of the OS in moderating The relationship of CSE to the three outcome variables (JSAT, OC, and JP). From the figure, it is clear that the OS neither plays an important role in CSE's relationship

Table 1: Validity test results.

Validity Test Results							
Variable	Item**	Score	Explanation	Variable	Item	Score	Explanation
			(r count)**				(r count)
CSE	1	0.803	legitimate	JP	3.1	0.692	legitimate
	2	0.292	legitimate		3.2	0.695	legitimate
	3	0.817	legitimate		3.3	0.718	legitimate
	4	0.657	legitimate		3.4	0.765	legitimate
JSAT	1.1	0.548	legitimate	3.5	0.691	legitimate	
	1.2	0.567	legitimate	1	0.539	legitimate	
	1.3	0.688	legitimate	2	0.561	legitimate	
	1.4	0.332	legitimate	3	0.678	legitimate	
	1.5	0.629	legitimate	4	0.34	legitimate	
OC	2.1	0.542	legitimate	OS	5	0.627	legitimate
	2.2	0.565	legitimate				
	2.3	0.691	legitimate				
	2.4	0.328	legitimate				
	2.5	0.63	legitimate				

to OC and JP, neither influence nor contributes to the relationship between CSE and JSAT.

Karman said that to determine the strength of the human resource system, the conceptual framework is important to link the suitability of human resource management (SHRM) with organizational values [18]. In line with that, the results of this analysis contribute greatly to the development of the management of the human system (HSM) and in line with the view of Karman.

Theoretical implications

The results of this study focus on two things. First, its finding is that CSE is an important factor in increasing job-outcomes (JSA, OC, and JP). The CSE concept has close links with the development of human resources through a human management system. Individual positive behavior can have a positive impact on the welfare of others. People who have a high sense of self-evaluation will reason more positively about themselves and have high confidence in their inherent abilities.

Second, the human management system requires the concept of ongoing organizational socialization (OS), because this can have an impact on job-outcomes. A qualified OS is a concept of the human management system. So there is CSE and OS synergy that causes responses from both OC and JP. The results of this study agree with previous research.

Practical implications

Findings of the study can have implications for the world of practice because they are closely related to managerial work systems in an organization [19]. To achieve organizational goals, managerial efforts must be supported by reliable human resource factors, which must be strengthened with their level of job satisfaction, concrete organizational commitment, and ever-increasing performance.

In the implementation of human management systems, CSE and OS must be an important concern for decision makers, because these two concepts are very relevant in efforts that assist in increasing job-outcomes [20]. According to Judge & Kammeyer-Mueller there is a need for individuals who possess the confidence and firmness to adapt, and bring forward the development of positive change in organizations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of testing the validity of this study found r count (score) $>$ r table for each construct, where r table at $n = 159$, $p 0.05$ amounted to 0.155. Also, based on the results of Pearson product-moments showed that all indicator variables were significant at $p < 0.05$ (2-tailed) (see Table 1). From these results, it can be said that all constructs studied have met the validity criteria and can be analyzed into the regression model.

The reliability test is measuring the level of reliability of research instruments which are indicators of a construct. An instrument is said to be reliable if the answers given by the respondents did not change from time to time. This study used Cronbach's alpha assessment technique, where if the results of the analysis show a Cronbach's Alpha value $>$ 0.70 then the research instrument is declared to be reliable. The results of this study's data analysis found that the Cronbach's Alpha value for each construct (X: 0.73; Y1: 0.76; Y2: 0.83; Y3: 0.86; and Z: 0.86), were $>$ 0.70. The Indication of these results is that all construct indicators have

reliability criteria and can be analyzed into regression models.

CONCLUSION

From the results of the analysis of research data it can be concluded that organizational socialization (OS) is proven to have demonstrated itself as an integral factor in moderating the relationship between core self-evaluation (CSE) and organizational commitment (OC), and towards job performance (JP). In other words the OS can strengthen the influence between CSE on OC and JP, but the OS has not been proven to moderate the influence of CSE on JSAT, unless it tends to weaken the relationship. Furthermore, the findings of this study demonstrated a positive and significant effect between CSE on all job-outcomes (JSAT, OC, and JP).

Some of the limitations of this research include the aspects of the unit of analysis that focus on new workers, then aspects of the object of research are limited to non-profit public organizations, although the benefits of the results of this study are quite relevant to the development of human resources where the research is conducted, but we consider the scope of the research location to be still limited.

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